

Research article

First record of a fossil spittlebug (Hemiptera: Auchenorrhyncha: Aphrophoridae) in Miocene deposits in Bulgaria

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Abstract: The first fossil record of a spittlebug affiliated to *Aphrophora* Germar, 1821 (Hemiptera: Cercopoidea: Aphrophoridae) is reported from Bulgaria (Western Rhodopes, Satovcha Graben). The fossil from Middle Miocene deposits represents the first recorded evidence of fossil Auchenorrhyncha in Bulgaria. A forewing illustration of the new finding and review of known fossils of *Aphrophora* are provided.

Keywords: *Aphrophora*, Bulgaria, Cercopoidea, fossil, Miocene, Rhodopes

Introduction

The Satovcha Graben is recognised as a significant Middle Miocene deposit of plant and insect fossils in Bulgaria (Bozukov, 2001, 2002; Bozukov & Ivanova, 2015; Ivanov, 2004, 2012, 2013; Nel et al., 2016; Simov et al., 2021a, 2021b). Recently, three new species of dragonflies (Odonata), a jewel beetle (Buprestidae), and a March fly (Bibionidae) have been described or recorded from this site (Nel et al., 2016; Simov et al., 2021a, 2021b). Nonetheless, numerous insect remains from various taxa in these deposits remain unexplored (Nel et al., 2016).

Here we present the first data on a Miocene fossil insect belonging to the genus *Aphrophora* (Hemiptera, Cercopoidea, Aphrophoridae) from Bulgaria. Thus, it represents the first documented fossil of Auchenorrhyncha in Bulgaria.

Material and methods

The studied fossil specimen was collected during a palaeobotanical expedition in the vicinity of the village of Satovcha in the period 1958–1967 by D. Jordanoff, P. Hadjiev and E. Palamarev, and by E. Palamarev in the beginning of the 1980s. (Fig. 1). The fossil insects reported here were discovered in the Sivik Formation of the Satovcha Graben. The Sivik Formation overlays the Oligocene volcanic strata and sediments of the Satovcha Formation. The sedimentary rocks of the Sivik Formation, characterised by sandstones, aleurolites, sandy clays and diatomites interspersed with coal streaks (Vatsev & Pirumova, 1983; Vatsev, 1999; Ivanov, 2013). Since the fossil insect under study originated from the lower part of the Sivik Formation, its age should be considered to fall within the Middle Miocene, approximately 16 to 11.6

Fig. 1. Geological map of the Satovcha Graben (after Vatshev & Pirumova, 1983) and the location of the fossil site (F). Legend: 1. Breccia and conglomerates (Quaternary). 2. Sivik Formation (Miocene). 3. Rhyolites and Rhyodacites (Oligocene). 4. Satovcha Formation (Oligocene). 5. Stamatitsa Member of Satovcha Formation (Sands). 6. Palashka Member of Satovcha Formation. 7. Bedding of Satovcha Formation (Proterozoic metamorphic rocks). 8. Faults.

million years ago (for the age of the Sivik Formation, see Bozukov, 2002; Ivanov, 2004, 2012, 2013; Nel et al., 2016).

The specimen under study is preserved as a compression fossil in diatomite clay with only minor relief. It is deposited in the collection of the Division of Palaeobotany and Palynology at the Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (IBER-BAS).

The photograph of the fossil was captured using a Canon EOS R50 camera with a Laowa 90mm F2.8 CA-Dreamer 2X Macro lens. A modified lighting system was employed for illumination. A total of 24 images were taken at different focal planes using a WeMacro motorised rail, which facilitated the automated and precise capture of image sequences with partial focus. To merge these images into a single fully focused image, Helicon Focus 8.1.0 software was used for post-processing. For vectorisation of the

venation on the fossil's wing, the captured photograph was used as a base. The vein patterns were manually traced using Inkscape, a free and open-source vector graphics editor. To create a comparative reference, a wing from a previously identified specimen of *Aphrophora alni* (Fallén, 1805) was carefully removed. The detached wing was mounted on an entomological board with entomological glue and then attached to an entomological pin for further analysis. A photograph of the mounted wing was taken under a DZ.1100 stereomicroscope with DZ.9005 photo tube attachment and a 5 Mp SCMOS camera. This image was then processed in Inkscape, where the veins were traced using the same methodology applied to the fossil. For naming the wing venation we used Evans (1966) and Shih & Yang (2005).

Results and discussion

Systematic palaeontology

Superfamily Cercopoidea Leach, 1815

Family Aphrophoridae Amyot & Serville, 1843

Subfamily Aphrophorinae Amyot et Serville, 1843

Genus *Aphrophora* Germar, 1821

Aphrophora sp. (Fig. 2)

Description

Cat-H-1 (part) (Fig. 2): A medium to large-sized spittlebug, measuring 14 mm in length, is dorsolaterally embedded and strongly compressed. The fossil appears as an imprint showing the dorsal side of the specimen, with a body shape resembling extant species of the genus *Aphrophora*. The body is ochraceous to brown with darker stripes and shaded areas on the wings. The head is wider than it is long, measuring 0.9 mm in length and 3.4 mm in width, with a well-defined median keel visible on the posterior two-thirds. The vertex is also wider than it is long, and while the frontal plate is visible, it is somewhat indistinct. The pronotum is transverse, 2.7 mm in length and 3.4 mm in width, with a median keel matching the head in width. The venation of left forewing is clearly visible (Fig. 3). The wing measures 12.7 mm in length. Adjacent to the spittlebug imprint, the rock also preserves a leaf imprint of *Carpinus grandis* Unger.

Fig. 2. *Aphrophora* sp. – Cat-H-1 Division of Palaeobotany and Palynology, Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia, Bulgaria. The scale corresponds to 1 cm.

Fig. 3. Wing venation.

A: Fossil *Aphrophora* sp., with dotted lines indicating the assumed lines that are not well visible on the fossil.

B: *Aphrophora alni*. A2 – second anal vein, A1 – first anal vein, Cls – clavus, Cu – cubital vein, Cu1 – first cubital branch, Cu1b – basal cubital branch, Cu1a – anterior cubital branch, ap4 – apical cell fourth, M – medial vein, m + cu – formed by the median and first cubital, ap3 – apical cell third, Sc – subcostal vein, Rs – radial sector vein, R1 – radius first, m + r – formed by the median and radial sector, ap2 – apical cell second, ap1 – apical cell first.

Remarks

The combination of the following features shows that the spittlebug undoubtedly belongs to family Aphrophoridae: the moderate size, tegulae absent, presence of well visible frontal plate, head and pronotum are equally broad and have a median keel, pronotum with more or less parallel sides, eye not reaching forewing base, (Dietrich, 2005; Anufriev & Emeljanov, 1988).

In general habitus the fossil spittlebug resembles much more representatives of the genus *Aphrophora* Germar, 1821. Most of the left forewing is clearly visible, showing partial pigmentation with two pale areas along the costal margin, and the venation resembling features seen in *Aphrophora alni*. The incomplete preservation of the specimen does not allow species description or affiliation to exact species.

The earliest records of the superfamily Cercopoidea, to which this fossil belongs, are thought to date back to the Triassic period (Dietrich, 2009). Further evidence suggests that members of the Aphrophoridae and Cercopidae families emerged during the Middle Cretaceous period. In the southern hemisphere, fossils from the Late Cretaceous and Early Palaeogene found in the Orapa deposits confirm the presence of Cercopoidea during these periods (Szwedo, 2008). During the PETM (Palaeocene-Eocene Thermal Maximum) and the Eocene greenhouse world, both Cercopidae and Aphrophoridae extended as far north as Greenland (Szwedo, 2008). As the climate transitioned and became cooler and drier during the Eocene/Oligocene period, these groups, which are currently associated with wet, tropical, and subtropical regions, were found in much more northern localities (Szwedo, 2008). Notably, Cercopidae and Aphrophoridae fossils have also been recorded in the Isle of Wight deposits (Szwedo, 2008). By the Miocene, Cercopoidea fossils were found in Oeningen and Rott in Germany, indicating their continued presence in these regions (Szwedo, 2008).

Aphrophora Germar, 1821 is a genus of spittlebugs with 109 extant (Dmitriev et. al., 2024; Soulier-Perkins, 2024) and 15 fossil species described worldwide (Mindat.org, 2024). Note that †*Aphrophora carbonaria* Germar & Berendt, 1856, was recently transferred to the genus *Ptyelus* Le Peletier & Audinet-Serville, 1828 (Dmitriev et. al., 2024). All fossil species except †*A. angusta* Handlirsch, 1910 and †*A. protocalla* Cockerell, 1925 have been described from Europe (Paleobiology Database, 2024). Most fossil

species have been found in Eocene and Oligocene strata, with only one species, *A. pitoni* Dmitriev, 2020, in the Upper Palaeocene deposits of France (Dmitriev, 2020). Until now three *Aphrophora* species from the Middle Miocene are established: †*A. stavropolitana* (Becker-Migdisova, 1964) from the Far East of Russia, †*A. spumarioides* Heer, 1853 from Germany and †*A. ungeri* (Heer, 1853) from Croatia. *A. ungeri* (Heer, 1853) is the closest to our specimen in age and geographical distribution (Paleobiology Database, 2024). There are some differences in wing venation (see Pongrácz (1928) for the wing venation of *A. ungeri*) that lead us to conclude that this could be a different species.

The genus currently has three extant species that occur in the Balkan Peninsula: *A. alni* (Fallén, 1805), *A. salicina* (Goeze, 1778), and *A. corticea* Germar, 1821. All three species are dendrobionts. The most widespread species, *A. alni*, is broadly polyphagous and feeds on a variety of deciduous trees. *A. salicina* is less polyphagous, while *A. corticea* is monophagous and feeds only on *Pinus* (Angelova & Gjonov, 2024).

The Middle Miocene Climatic Optimum (MMCO) (17–15 million years ago) was a period of global warmth and relatively high CO₂ levels and was thought to be associated with a significant retreat of the Antarctic Ice Sheet (Foster et al., 2012). MMCO influence was the reason for the exceptional taxonomic diversity in the palaeoflora on the territory of Bulgaria during the Middle Miocene (Palamarev, 1964, 1989; Palamarev & Petkova, 1987; Bozukov, 2001). The local palaeoflora from Satovcha, the richest in the region with over 140 taxa, is supported by new data (Bozukov & Ivanova, 2015; Bozukov et al., 2018, 2022, 2023a, 2023b; Hristova & Bozukov, 2018; Bozukov & Todorov, 2021), which confirm the coexistence of palaeotropical and arctotertiary elements in this flora as first reported by Bozukov (2001). The favourable climatic conditions during the Middle Miocene made possible the successful development of both types of elements in the same area at the same time. The different tree and shrub genera recorded in the locality as *Quercus*, *Carpinus*, *Salix*, *Betula*, *Populus*, *Crataegus*, *Pinus* (Bozukov, 1998a, 1998b, 1999a, 1999b, 2000) fit very well with the food preference of extant dendrobiont *Aphrophora* species, especially all Bulgarian representatives.

Future studies in Satovcha and other middle Miocene palaeoflora localities: Chukurovo (Pala-

marev, 1964, 1989) and Ruzhintsi (Palamarev & Petkova, 1987) could be very important filling the gaps in our knowledge of the formation of the modern faunal complexes in the Balkan Peninsula. Additionally a special attention will be needed to a recently re-discovered middle Miocene locality – Underwater Petrified Forest natural phenomenon, Sozopol Bay, Black Sea (Velev et al., 2023).

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